

ON THE USE OF POTASSIUM HYDROXIDE AS A BASE IN ACETONE MEDIUM

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In effecting the N-alkylation of amides, the usefulness of potassium hydroxide in dry acetone medium as a base was first reported by Pachter and Kloetzel (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 1321) and subsequently by Latif and Sattar (this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 489). In course of the present investigation, attempts were made to find out the factor behind the effectiveness of 'KOH-acetone' as a base. Using *p* nitroacetunilide, two series of experiments were performed, changing only one parameter at a time (*i.e.*, either the base or the reaction medium), and it was observed that weaker bases like lime, baryta or sodium carbonate were of no use whereas dry sodium ethoxide gave fairly good results (all in acetone medium). On the other hand, using KOH in other ketonic solvent medium, such as cyclohexanone and diacetone alcohol (the latter obviously producing acetone in the medium), fairly good results were obtained (yield 60% and 75% respectively). However, non-polar solvents like benzene, ether, etc. were practically useless.

It has been further observed that 'KOH-acetone' also may be employed successfully for effecting certain base-catalysed reactions where normally sodium and alcohol are used, *e.g.*, in the alkylation (both mono- and di-) of malonic ester, cyanoacetic ester, phenylacetone, etc. At least in the alkylation of phenylacetone, this base has been found to be superior to sodium and alcohol, because in presence of the latter, such an alkylation has been reported to be unsuccessful (Suter and Weston, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 533). Also from the data so far available, it appears that this base can effect condensation between malonic ester and ethylene bromide (Perkin's ring-closure) and malonic ester and benzalacetone (Michael condensation). Further works on these are in progress.

A probable explanation of the effectiveness of the base 'KOH-acetone' may be given as follows:

Acetone is likely to come to equilibrium with its corresponding anion (I) whenever a base is added to it:

The equilibrium will, of course, be far to the left. However, if a second compound 'AH' is added, which has at least one H atom more protonic in nature than that of acetone, a reaction will immediately take place, forming the anion (III):

It is this anion which will react further, depending on the condition.

Ethylation of Malonic Ester using 'KOH-Acetone' as the Base.—Freshly distilled malonic ester (8 g., 0.03M) was dissolved in 100 c.c. of dry acetone and to this dry powdered KOH (5.6 g., 0.1M) was added. The mixture was brought to the reflux temperature of acetone, and ethyl iodide (9.4 g., 0.06M), dissolved in 10 c.c. of dry acetone, was added and the whole mixture was refluxed for 2 hours. The solution was then filtered while hot and the acetone was distilled off. Excess of water was added and the mixture was extracted with ether. The ether was then evaporated off and the residue dried over CaCl_2 and distilled under reduced pressure. The bulk of the product distilled at $84^\circ/7$ mm, yield 8.2 g. (88%); $n_D^{20} 1.4103$, $d_4^{20} 0.9903$. Calculated value of molecular refraction is 47.08 (Found 47.2).

Reaction with other active methylene compounds were carried out similarly.

Methylation of Phenylacetone.—The experimental procedure was identical as above and the time of reflux was 2 hours; yield 80%; b.p. of the product $78^\circ/5$ mm, $n_D^{20} 1.5084$, $d_4^{20} 0.9980$. Molecular refraction calculated for 1:1-methylphenylacetone is 44.8 (Found 44.2). Semicarbazone, m.p. 172° (agrees with the literature value, *Ann. chim. phys.*, 1907, viii, 10, 362).

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